

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 2. Information of the collections used in the analyses for the Phylogeny S4. Holotypes and paratypes are indicated by HT and PT, respectively; note that the paratypes of a species are only indicated when its holotype is not present.

(1) Ingroup

Genera	Species	Voucher Nos.	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>rpb2</i>	<i>tef-1a</i>	
<i>Abstoma</i>	<i>Ab. indicum</i>	CAL1866	India	OL454195	-	-	-	Altaf <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Ab. purpureum</i>	KM162954	Unknown	GQ981488	-	-	-	Bidartondo <i>et al.</i> (2009)
<i>Agaricus</i>	<i>Ag. campestris</i>	LAPAG370	Spain	KM657927	KR006607	KT951556	KR006636	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Ag. comtulus</i>	LAPAG724	Spain	KT951332	KT951448	KT951532	KT951593	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Ag. flocculosipes</i>	JM03-193	Thailand	KT951325	-	KT951555	KT951617	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Ag. gennadii</i>	CA339	Unknown	KT951318	-	KT951547	KT951575	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Ag. lanipedisimilis</i>	ZRL2012151	China	KT951366	KT951484	-	KT951578	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Apioperdon</i>	<i>Ap. pyriforme</i>	AFTOL-ID 480	Unknown	AY854075	-	AY218495	AY883426	Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Ap. pyriforme</i>	HAI-G-159	Israel	OR594093	-	-	-	Krakhmalnyi <i>et al.</i> (2023)
<i>Arachnion</i>	<i>Ar. album</i>	TNS:F-82296	Japan	OQ025256	OQ025240	-	-	Kasuya <i>et al.</i> (2023)
<i>Asperosporus</i>	<i>As. subterraneus</i>	FLAS-F-68001 (HT)	USA	MW775328	MW773843	MW816922	MW816921	Karlsen-Ayala <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Barcheria</i>	<i>Ba. willisiana</i>	MEL2177563	Australia	JF495036	AY372216	-	-	Lebel <i>et al.</i> (2004)
<i>Battarrea</i>	<i>Be. phalloides</i>	KRMK10 (ITS) & KRBAT21 (nrLSU)	India	MN450310	MN700164	-	-	Kantharaja & Krishnappa (2020)
<i>Battarreoides</i>	<i>Bo. diguetii</i>	MO519776	USA	OR614764	-	-	-	Direct submission by Clements
<i>Bovista</i>	<i>Bv. litangensis</i>	HMAS258800 (HT)	China	OR792635	OR831301	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Bv. nyalamensis</i>	HMAS258836 (HT)	China	OR792637	OR831304	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Bovistella</i>	<i>Bt. emodensis</i>	HMAS287485 (HT)	China	PP175744	PP175752	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Bt. utrififormis</i>	MJ5388	Sweden	DQ112607	DQ112607	-	-	Larsson & Jeppson (2008)
<i>Bryoperdon</i>	<i>Br. acuminatum</i>	TO HG191016	Italy	KY581201	KY581199	-	-	Vizzini & Ercole (2017)
	<i>Br. acuminatum</i>	HMAS258888	China	OR792632	OR831232	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Calvatia</i>	<i>Ca. cyathiformis</i>	HTBM0912	China	PP736664	PP732894	PP746798	PP746828	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Ca. gigantea</i>	HTBM0403	China	PP736659	PP732890	PP746795	PP746823	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Ca. holothurioides</i>	HTBM0906	China	PP736663	PP732893	-	PP746827	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Ca. longisetulosa</i>	HMAS258802 (HT)	Thailand	OR792617	OR831229	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Ca. shennongjiaensis</i>	HMAS258806 (HT)	China	OR792623	OR831291	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Candelolepiota</i>	<i>Cd. sinica</i>	HTBM1241	China	PQ321882	PQ319808	PQ329236	PQ329247	This study
	<i>Cd. sinica</i>	HTBM2008	China	PQ321874	PQ319800	PQ329229	PQ329237	This study
<i>Chamaemyces</i>	<i>Ce. fracidus</i>	X-1977	Belgium	AY176343	AY176344	-	-	Vellinga (2004)
<i>Chlamydropus</i>	<i>Cm. meyenianus</i>	AH18743	Unknown	AF097755	-	-	-	Martín & Johannesson (2000b)
<i>Chlorophyllum</i>	<i>Ch. agaricoides</i>	HKAS101312	Russia	MG742003	MG742020	MG742050	MG742078	Ge <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Ch. molybdites</i>	HKAS45051	China	MG741985	MG742030	MG742059	MG742087	Ge <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Clarkeinda</i>	<i>Cr. trachodes</i>	ECV3550	Thailand	HM488751	-	HM488802	-	Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Coniolepiota</i>	<i>Co. spongodes</i>	ECV3898	Thailand	HM488756	HM488774	HM488796	HM488883	Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Co. aff. spongodes</i>	ECV3613	Thailand	HM488757	-	HM488797	HM488881	Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Coprinus</i>	<i>Cp. comatus</i>	AFTOL-ID 626	Unknown	AY854066	AY635772	AY780934	AY881026	Lutzoni <i>et al.</i> (2004)
	<i>Cp. littoralis</i>	AH45819 (HT)	Spain	KU686920	KU686903	-	-	Crous <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Cp. pinetorum</i>	AH44094 (HT)	Spain	KU686924	KU686907	-	-	Crous <i>et al.</i> (2016)
<i>Cystolepiota</i>	<i>Cy. hetieri</i>	HKAS84189	China	MN810139	MN810094	MN820976	MN820916	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cy. pseudofumosifolia</i>	HKAS105918	China	MN810152	MN810108	MN820974	MN820920	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cy. pyramidosquamulosa</i>	HKAS53985 (HT)	China	OP059088	OP059068	OP104335	OP141792	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cy. seminuda</i>	HKAS84275	China	OP059093	OP059072	OP104340	OP141796	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
<i>Dictyocephalos</i>	<i>Di. attenuatus</i>	AH19028	Spain	AF095688	-	-	-	Martín <i>et al.</i> (2000a)
	<i>Di. xinjiangensis</i>	HMAS55794 (HT)	China	MZ047791	MZ047793	-	-	Hyde <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Disciseda</i>	<i>Ds. bovista</i>	MJ5078	Sweden	DQ112627	DQ112627	-	-	Larsson & Jeppson (2008)
	<i>Ds. sp.</i>	BJTC06072350	China	OR792633	OR831295	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Echinoderma</i>	<i>Ec. asperum</i>	HKAS105694	China	MN810153	MN810106	MN820966	MN820908	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Ec. flavidoasperum</i>	HKAS87905 (HT)	China	MN810147	MN810098	MN820969	MN820903	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
<i>Eriocybe</i>	<i>Er. chionea</i>	ECV3560	Thailand	HM488752	HM488773	HM488800	-	Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Fuscospina</i>	<i>F. scabricapillitia</i>	HMAS258812 (HT)	China	OR792678	PP175748	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>F. nigrescens</i>	HMAS258881	China	OR792702	OR831256	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Globaria</i>	<i>G. cf. aestivalis</i>	HTBM0371	China	PP736658	PP732889	PP746794	PP746822	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>G. jingningensis</i>	HMAS258817 (PT)	China	OR792642	OR831271	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>G. muscicola</i>	HMAS258835 (HT)	China	OR792641	OR831268	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Holocotylon</i>	<i>Ho. biconicum</i>	HMAS258778 (HT)	China	OR792667	OR831266	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Ho. purpurascens</i>	HMAS258780 (PT)	China	OR792671	OR831300	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Hymenagaricus</i>	<i>Hy. ardosicolor</i>	LAPAF9	Togo	JF727840	-	-	-	Mwanga & Tibuhwa (2014)
	<i>Hy. floccosus</i>	QaL-22-2 (HT)	Pakistan	PP413741	PP413742	-	PP434430	Nawaz <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Hy. saisamornae</i>	SDBRCMUNK0369 (HT)	Thailand	MW345912	MW345917	-	-	Kumla <i>et al.</i> (2021)
	<i>Hy. splendidissimus</i>	HTBM1385	China	PP736734	PP732964	PP746792	PP746820	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Lepiota</i>	<i>Lp. alba</i>	HKAS90371	China	MN810115	MN810075	MN820946	MN820930	Hou & Ge (2020)
	<i>Lp. castanea</i>	HKAS84179	China	MN810119	MN810077	MN820960	MN820914	Hou & Ge (2020)
	<i>Lp. clypeolaria</i>	HKAS87248	China	MN810123	MN810080	MN820941	MN820932	Hou & Ge (2020)
	<i>Lp. echinacea</i>	HKAS105582	China	MN810155	MN810104	MN820954	MN820928	Hou & Ge (2020)
	<i>Lp. geocarpa</i>	UTC00143916	USA	HQ020412	EU130550	MN820945	MN820935	Hou & Ge (2020)
	<i>Lp. omninoflava</i>	HKAS106734 (HT)	China	MN810157	MN810092	MN820951	MN820923	Hou & Ge (2020)
<i>Leptocaulis</i>	<i>Lu. ericaeus</i>	KA13-1463	South Korea	KP340185	-	KU764396	KU764404	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Lu. sublongistipes</i>	HMAS258775 (PT)	China	OR792741	OR831318	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Lu. subumbrinus</i>	HMAS258885	China	OR792673	OR831315	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Lu. badius</i>	LAH-SH148 (HT)	Pakistan	KU647736	KU900518	KU900506	KU900510	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Leucoagaricus</i>	<i>La. lahorensiformis</i>	LAHSH-L2 (HT)	Pakistan	KU647729	KU900517	KU900509	KU900511	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Lc. amanitoides</i>	E.C.Vellinga 3331 (PT)	USA	EF080869	EF080873	-	HM488933	Vellinga & Davis (2006); Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Leucocoprinus</i>	<i>Lc. barssii</i>	ECV3126	USA	DQ911600	DQ911601	DQ911602	GU187722	Lutzoni <i>et al.</i> (2004); Binder <i>et al.</i> (2010)
	<i>Lc. birnbaumii</i>	HTBM1220	China	PQ321881	PQ319807	PQ329235	PQ329246	This study
	<i>Lc. cretaceus</i>	HTBM0214	China	PQ321877	PQ319803	PQ329232	PQ329240	This study
	<i>Lc. leucothites</i>	HMAS88854	China	EU416308	EU416309	JN993680	-	Liang <i>et al.</i> (2010); direct submission by Ge
	<i>Ld. tianzhuensis</i>	HMAS258766	China	OR792725	OR831324	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Lycoperdiscus</i>	<i>Ld. lividus</i>	MJ4005	Sweden	DQ112600	-	-	-	Larsson & Jeppson (2008)

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Genera	Species	Voucher Nos.	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>rpb2</i>	<i>tef-1a</i>	
<i>Lycoperdon</i>	<i>Ly. perlatum</i>	HMAS258866	China	OR792763	OR831257	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Ly. perlatum</i>	KA13-0555	China	KP340193	-	KU764393	KU764403	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Ly. subperlatum</i>	HMAS258873	China	OR792751	OR831261	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Macrolepiota</i>	<i>Ma. dolichaula</i>	HKAS59721 (ITS), HKAS50547 (nrLSU & <i>rpb2</i>) & AFTOL-ID 481 (<i>tef-1a</i>)	China	JN180325	JN940269	JN993700	DQ435785	Direct submission by Ge; Ge <i>et al.</i> (2012); Matheny <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Ma. excoriata</i>	HAI-233-1	Israel	JQ683098	-	-	KC884703	Barseghyan <i>et al.</i> (2012)
<i>Macropsalliota</i>	<i>Mc. americanus</i>	ECV2454 (ITS & nrLSU) & S. Sheine (UC) (<i>rpb2</i> & <i>tef-1a</i>)	USA	AY176407	AF482891	HM488809	HM488888	Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2003); Vellinga (2004); Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Mc. subtropica</i>	HTBM0913	China	PQ321884	PQ319810	-	PQ329241	This study
<i>Melanophyllum</i>	<i>Me. haematospermum</i>	ECV2249 (ITS & nrLSU) & H.s Bender 6280 (<i>rpb2</i> & <i>tef-1a</i>)	Netherlands	AF391038	AY176455	HM488818	HM488947	Vellinga (2001); Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Micropsalliota</i>	<i>Mi. albofelina</i>	HKAS70329	China	OR799877	OR799922	OR962218	OR962180	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Mi. cortinata</i>	HKAS92221	China	OR799879	OR799924	OR962220	OR962183	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Mi. furfuracea</i>	HKAS60229	China	OR799889	OR799934	OR962229	OR962201	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Mi. geesterani</i>	AH47609	UK	KM923965	KM923966	-	-	Parra <i>et al.</i> (2016)
	<i>Mi. megarubescens</i>	HKAS60253	China	OR799900	OR799945	OR962237	OR962189	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Mi. nana</i>	HKAS114619	China	OR799901	OR799946	OR962238	OR962216	Gao <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Montagnea</i>	<i>Mo. arenaria</i>	MEL262622	Australia	OK159914	-	-	-	Direct submission by Lebel, May, Holmes & Davoodian
	<i>Mo. candollei</i>	CBS326.51	Argentina	MH856879	MH868400	-	-	Vu <i>et al.</i> (2019)
<i>Morganella</i>	<i>Mr. arenicola</i>	UFRN-Fungos 1006 (HT)	Brazil	KU958303	KU958304	-	-	Alfredo <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Mr. tricolor</i>	HMAS287487 (HT)	China	PP175741	PP175750	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>My. corium</i>	MJ5467	Sweden	DQ112628	DQ112628	-	-	Larsson & Jeppson (2008)
<i>Phellorinia</i>	<i>Ph. herculeana</i>	BCC-MPM1050	Spain	AF097753	-	-	-	Martín <i>et al.</i> (2000a)
	<i>Ph. longistriatica</i>	HMAS255795 (HT)	China	MZ047792	MZ047794	-	-	Hyde <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Podaxis</i>	<i>Po. namibensis</i>	PRUM4366 (HT)	Namibia	OP739195	-	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Po. pistillaris</i>	FH 374341 (ITS) & PC Bethke 6237 (<i>rpb2</i> & <i>tef-1a</i>)	USA	OP739130	-	HM488811	HM488956	Vellinga <i>et al.</i> (2011); Li <i>et al.</i> (2023)
<i>Pseudolepiota</i>	<i>Ps. zangmui</i>	Ge2175	China	KY768928	MG742049	KY768929	MG742106	Ge <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Pseudoperdon</i>	<i>Pp. medogense</i>	HMAS258784 (PT)	China	OR792745	OR831254	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Pp. subcretaceum</i>	MJ9032	Norway	JN572908	-	-	-	Jeppson <i>et al.</i> (2012)
<i>Pulverolepiota</i>	<i>Pu. oliveirae</i>	HKAS124759	China	OP059089	OP059069	OP104336	OP141793	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pu. petasiformis</i>	ECV1872	UK	AF391036	AY176349	-	-	Qu <i>et al.</i> (2023)
<i>Sinoperdon</i>	<i>Sp. gyirongense</i>	HMAS258787 (HT)	China	OR792686	OR831248	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>Sp. maritimum</i>	HMAS287488 (HT)	Thailand	OR792626	OR831234	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Smithiomyces</i>	<i>Sm. dominicanus</i>	JBSD126144	Dominica	KR604686	MW716266	MW736563	MW736558	Ge <i>et al.</i> (2021)
	<i>Sm. heterosporus</i>	HKAS84392	China	MW522985	MW716268	MW736565	MW736560	Ge <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>Tulostoma</i>	<i>T. brumale</i>	Eckblad (O-58849)	Norway	KU519062	KU519062	-	KU843949	Jeppson <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>T. fimbriatum</i>	Finy 8	Hungary	KU518968	KU518968	-	KU843912	Jeppson <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>T. grandisporum</i>	Jeppson 8907 (HT)	Hungary	KU519003	KU519003	-	KU843924	Jeppson <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>T. kotlabae</i>	Jeppson 7441	Denmark	KU519026	KU519026	-	KU843975	Jeppson <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>T. punctatum</i>	Jeppson 7472	Slovakia	KU518952	KU518952	-	KU843875	Jeppson <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>Utraria</i>	<i>U. mammiformis</i>	HMAS258845	China	OR792712	OR831331	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>U. nivea</i>	HMAS258839	China	OR792730	OR831312	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Vascellum</i>	<i>Va. curtisii</i>	MJ5880	Czech Republic	DQ112556	DQ112556	-	-	Larsson & Jeppson (2008)
	<i>Va. pratense</i>	HMAS258880	China	OR792665	OR831258	-	-	Li <i>et al.</i> (2024)
<i>Verrucospora</i>	<i>Ve. flavofusca</i>	HKAS41933	China	DQ241779	DQ470825	-	-	Matheny <i>et al.</i> (2006)
<i>Xanthagaricus</i>	<i>X. chamaeleontinus</i>	HTBM0824	China	PP736701	PP732931	PP746784	PP746803	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>X. erinaceus</i>	HTBM0936	China	PP736704	PP732934	PP746788	PP746812	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>X. heinemannii</i>	HKAS133458 (HT)	China	PP736714	PP732944	PP746799	PP746829	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>X. phylononcaeruleus</i>	HKAS133456 (HT)	China	PP736698	PP732928	PP746785	PP746804	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>X. purpureosquamulosus</i>	HTBM1932	China	PP736667	PP732897	PP746801	PP746832	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>X. retisporus</i>	HTBM1315	China	PP736654	PP732885	PP746791	PP746815	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	<i>X. scauinus</i>	HTBM0714	China	PP736700	PP732930	PP746787	PP746808	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2024)

(2) Outgroup

Families	Species	Voucher Nos.	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>rpb2</i>	<i>tef-1a</i>	
Bolbitiaceae	<i>Bolbitius vitellinus</i>	AFTOL-ID 730	USA	DQ200920	AY691807	DQ385878	-	Lutzoni <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Cortinariaceae	<i>Cortinarius iodes</i>	AFTOL-ID 285	Unknown	AF389133	AY702013	AY536285	-	Lutzoni <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Galeropsidaceae	<i>Panaeolus papilionaceus</i>	ZRL2015022-1	Unknown	LT716041	KY418857	-	KY419060	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Hydnangiaceae	<i>Laccaria</i> sp.	ZRL20151663	Unknown	LT716039	KY418855	KY419002	KY419058	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Hymenogastraceae	<i>Gymnopilus picreus</i>	ZRL2015011	Unknown	LT716066	KY418882	KY419027	KY419077	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Nidulariaceae	<i>Nidularia deformis</i>	ZRL2015047-1	Unknown	LT716025	KY418840	-	KY419047	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Psathyrellaceae	<i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i>	ZRL20151400	Unknown	LT716063	KY418879	KY419024	KY419075	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Tubariaceae	<i>Tubaria vinicolor</i>	AFTOL-ID 499	Unknown	DQ536417	DQ536415	DQ536418	-	Lutzoni <i>et al.</i> (2004)